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Inadequate Numerical Skills in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022

It grew by 11.24% on average between 2018 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of inadequate numerical competence. This is a value calculated as the percentage of students in classes III of lower secondary school who do not reach a sufficient level (Level I + Level II of 5 Levels) of numerical competence. The data are produced by Invalsi as part of national learning surveys. The data refers to the period between 2018 and 2022. However, the data relating to 2020 are missing together with the historical series relating to the Trentino Alto Adige region.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of inadequate numerical skills in 2022. Calabria is in first place by value of inadequate numerical skills in 2022 with a value of 62.2, followed by Sicily with an amount of 61.7, and from Campania with an amount of 58.2. In the middle of the table are Abruzzo with an amount of 43.1, followed by Liguria with an amount of 42.7, and Piedmont with a value of 38.9 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a value of 33.5, followed by Veneto with 33.2 and Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 30.4 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in inadequate numerical skills between 2018 and 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia is in first place in terms of value of inadequate numerical skills between 2018 and 2022 with a value of 25.47 % equal to a variation from an amount of 26.70 units up to a value of 33.50 units. Lombardy follows with a variation equal to a value of 18.03% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 29.40 units up to a value of 34.70 units or equal to an amount of 5.30%. Below is Liguria with a variation equal to an amount of 17.31% equal to an amount from 36.40 units up to a value of 42.70 units or equal to an amount of 6.30 units.

In the middle of the table is Lazio with a change in inadequate numerical skills between 2018 and 2022 equal to a value of 13.28%, going from a value of 38.40 units up to a value of 43.50 units equal to an amount of 5.10 units. Piedmont follows with a variation equal to 12.75% equal to a variation from 34.50 units up to 38.90 units equivalent to a value of 4.40 units. Below there is also Umbria with a variation equal to an amount of 11.86% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 31.20 units up to a value of 43.90 units.

Calabria closes the ranking with a value equal to 6.69% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 58.30 units up to a value of 62.20 units equal to an amount of 3.90 units. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to 3.16% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 47.40 units up to a value of 48.90 units or equal to a value of 1.50 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 2.36% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 29.70 units up to a variation of 30.40 units equal to an amount of 0.70 units . On average, the value of inadequate numerical competence between 2018 and 2022 grew by 11.24% for the Italian regions or from 39.1 units up to 43.5 units.

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Inadequate numerical competence in the Italian macro regions between 2018 and 2022. Inadequate numerical competence in Northern Italy grew by 16.23% between 2018 and 2022, going from a value of 30.80 units up to a value of 35.80 units or equal to an amount of 5.00 units. Inadequate numerical competence in Central Italy grew by 13.64% between 2018 and 2022, going from a value of 35.20 units to a value of 40.00 units or equal to 4.80 units. The inadequate numerical competence in the South grew by 8.67% between 2018 and 2022 equivalent to a variation from a value of 51.90 units up to a value of 56.40 units equal to an amount of 4.50 unit.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Umbria, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Marche, Veneto, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Abruzzo, Lazio, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Sicily, Sardinia, Calabria, Basilicata, Puglia.

Cluster 2 appears to be dominant compared to cluster 1. The following ordering of the clusters therefore derives: $C2 > C1$. Cluster 2 is made up of almost all the southern regions with the exception of Abruzzo and Molise which are instead part of Cluster 1. It therefore follows that in most southern regions the value of inadequate numerical skills tends to be high compared to the corresponding value of the regions of Central-Northern Italy.

Conclusions. The value of inadequate numerical competence grew in all Italian regions by a value equal to 11.24% between 2018 and 2022. Considering the Italian macro-regions it is possible to note that 56.40% of southern students have an inadequate numerical competence, compared to 40.00% in Central Italy and 35.80% in Northern Italy. It therefore follows that Italian educational institutions lack the ability to increase students' numerical skills. We need to intervene with new education policies to increase students' numerical skills. In fact, the reduced numerical skills of students could generate a reduction in the human capital employed in STEM disciplines with a compression of the competitive capacity of the Italian regions in science, technology and innovation. To increase the competitive and productive capacity of the Italian economy, it is necessary to invest in STEM disciplines starting from schools with an increase in the numerical competence of students.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Competenza Numerica non Adeguata nelle Regioni Italiane							
Rank	Regione	2018	2019	2021	2022	Var As	Var Per
1	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 26,70	★ 28,50	★ 35,00	★ 33,50	★ 6,80	★ 25,47
2	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 29,40	★ 30,30	★ 36,60	★ 34,70	★ 5,30	★ 18,03
3	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 36,40	★ 35,00	★ 42,20	★ 42,70	★ 6,30	★ 17,31
4	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 28,80	★ 28,90	★ 33,70	★ 33,20	★ 4,40	★ 15,28
5	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 33,00	★ 33,80	★ 38,40	★ 37,90	★ 4,90	★ 14,85
6	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 37,80	★ 38,40	★ 43,60	★ 43,10	★ 5,30	★ 14,02
7	<i>Marche</i>	★ 30,10	★ 29,30	★ 35,30	★ 34,30	★ 4,20	★ 13,95
8	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 32,50	★ 33,10	★ 37,60	★ 36,90	★ 4,40	★ 13,54
9	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 38,40	★ 39,30	★ 43,90	★ 43,50	★ 5,10	★ 13,28
10	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 34,50	★ 34,70	★ 40,60	★ 38,90	★ 4,40	★ 12,75
11	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 31,20	★ 32,20	★ 38,20	★ 34,90	★ 3,70	★ 11,86
12	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 45,10	★ 44,70	★ 49,30	★ 50,30	★ 5,20	★ 11,53
13	<i>Molise</i>	★ 41,00	★ 43,40	★ 47,10	★ 45,00	★ 4,00	★ 9,76
14	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 56,60	★ 57,30	★ 61,60	★ 61,70	★ 5,10	★ 9,01
15	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 51,30	★ 51,00	★ 57,00	★ 55,30	★ 4,00	★ 7,80
16	<i>Campania</i>	★ 54,00	★ 54,10	★ 60,80	★ 58,20	★ 4,20	★ 7,78
17	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 58,30	★ 59,00	★ 63,20	★ 62,20	★ 3,90	★ 6,69
18	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 47,40	★ 45,20	★ 51,50	★ 48,90	★ 1,50	★ 3,16
19	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 29,70	★ 30,30	★ 35,60	★ 30,40	★ 0,70	★ 2,36

Competenza Numerica non Adeguata nelle Regioni Italiane						
Macro-Regioni Italiane	2018	2019	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	★ 30,80	★ 31,30	★ 37,00	★ 35,80	★ 5,00	★ 16,23
<i>Centro</i>	★ 35,20	★ 35,80	★ 40,70	★ 40,00	★ 4,80	★ 13,64
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	★ 51,90	★ 52,10	★ 58,00	★ 56,40	★ 4,50	★ 8,67
<i>Italia</i>	★ 39,30	★ 39,60	★ 44,50	★ 43,60	★ 4,30	★ 10,94

